

The Barcelona Museum of Music

JAUME AYATS – SARA GUASTEVI

The Barcelona Museum of Music (see WR 1) is dedicated to experimentation and reflection on musical activities. It is planned as a meeting point and a space for debate, knowledge and aesthetic enjoyment where the public can gain an understanding of how music plays a part in our individual and social emotions. The museum wants to be a space where visitors can relate with music and return time and time again. A place where museography makes a visit worthwhile and provides a gateway to other content or activities in our “city of music”, namely L’Auditori with a variety of concert programmes, the Escola Superior de Música de Catalunya (Catalan School of Music) and a library-space containing historical archives, sound recordings and other musical reference material.

Genesis and the inauguration at the conservatory

Catalan culture’s interest in “ancient musical instruments” was already evident at the exhibition of “decorative arts” in 1867 in Barcelona and at the 1888 Universal Barcelona Exhibition. Since then the idea of establishing a specific collection of musical instruments was forged and took the form of a proposal by the Museu del Teatre, presented by Marc Jesús Bertran to Barcelona City Council and the Mancomunitat de Catalunya in 1912, with a section dedicated to music.

The history of the collections of the Museu de la Música began in the year 1921, when the Municipal Commission for Culture accepted the donation offered by a group of music-loving patricians of Barcelona, in order to launch the project of a new Theatre,

Music and Dance Museum. That first collection soon expanded with new donations and in 1931 the greater part of the holdings went to the Theatre Institute. In 1932, the important collection of antique musical instruments was assigned under deposit to the Barcelona Museum Board. That assignment, promoted by Orsina Baget de Folch, substantially enlarged and enriched the initial collection. It was then that the Museum Board decided to found a small-scale Museum of Musical Instruments, located in what had been a pavilion of the royal residence of the King of Spain in Montjuïc Park from the International Exposition of 1929. Consequently, for the occasion it was called the Albéniz Pavilion, Antique Musical Instrument Museum, in memory of and as a permanent tribute to the great Catalan musician.

The advent of the Spanish Civil War brought the project to a halt and it was not until 1946 that Barcelona was to see the birth of the long-awaited *Museu de la Música*. It was accommodated in the Municipal School of Music on the street Bruc in Barcelona, which had become the Conservatory. Accordingly, in a ceremony presided over by the mayor, the Museum opened on 29 May 1946 under the direction of the distinguished professor Josep Ricart i Matas.

The decision to accommodate it in the School of Music was based on the Museum's founding objectives and its scientific and museological approach, considering it to be a complementary tool in the educational task of music classes, a promoter of scientific research among scholars and a means of disseminating music. Indeed, in the words of Tomàs Carreras i Artau (deputy mayor), the Museum was to be, «a highly efficient instrument in helping to reconstruct the series and the processes of the musical moments, a matter of the history of music, which cannot in any case be considered apart from the general history of culture or from the particular history of the diverse peoples».

Notable from the first period of the collection are the donations made by musicians and the rest of the civil society of Barcelona and Catalonia. These donations demonstrated the interest and response that institutions such as ours could arouse: the initial collection of some one hundred instruments tripled in the first three years alone.

In this way, together with the first collections and especially the magnificent Folch i Torres-Baget collection of antique instruments (the final purchase dates from the year 1947), holdings and singular pieces representative of European culture were added. Moreover, the expeditions to far-off cultures and countries which were promoted by the then director of the Ethnological Museum, August Panyella, and Eudald Serra, in the 1950s and 60s, provided a very considerable representation of African cultures (especially Equatorial Guinea), the Far East (especially Papua New Guinea) and Latin America. In the year 1969, the main collection already comprised 966 instruments. One year later, in 1970, the museum acquired the Francisco Arellano Collection, a very complete holding of phonographs, gramophones and archive material related to sound recording.

The Museu at the Palace of Baron of Quadras (1980-2001) and at L'Auditori (2007)

As a result of the growth of the Conservatory, in 1980 the Museum moved to Casa Quadras, a Modernista (Catalan Art Nouveau) (see WR 2) building by the architect Puig i Cadafalch which had been the home of the Baron of Quadras. The Museum displayed its collections, preserving the original structures and all the richness and authenticity of the exuberant Modernista decoration of the main floor. Under the direction of Romà Escalas i Llimona, the official re-inauguration of the Museu de la Música, on 11 February 1983, afforded the possibility of building a more complete museographical discourse and of opening the Museum more widely to the city, starting up a public programming of activities and services addressed to the various publics.

The complete catalogue of the instrument collection was published in 1991 under the technical direction of Escalas. The first catalogue of the Museum presented its over 1,300 instruments in an edition that was praised for its scientific quality. The publication marked a step forward in the normalisation of musical terminology and vernacular musical instrument designations, and in the adoption of the most universal criteria of systematised classification of the instrument families. At the same time it represented the explicit recognition of the curators and managers who had played a role in the more than 40 years of the collection's history.

In 1996, as the main event of the celebration of the fiftieth anniversary of the Museu de la Música, the exhibition *Els nostres luthiers, escultors del so* (Our luthiers, sculptors in sound) was held. It was devoted to the art of instrument-making. Through a specificity of content based on the Museum's collections, the exhibition presented the figure of the luthier and his art, revindicated as the maker of sound and the unquestioned agent who completes the unique composer-interpreter-luthier cycle in musical creation. It also represented the recognition of the Catalan luthiers by the international collective of experts.

In 2001, the Museu de la Música closed its doors to the public at Casa Quadras in order to prepare its collections for the new museological and museographical project in the Auditori building in Barcelona. There, at the beginning of 2007, the Museu reopened with its collections newly displayed.

The project of a large area devoted to music in Barcelona dates back to the end of the 1980s, in the context of the re-planning and development of the city's cultural amenities in the period prior to the 1992 Olympics. In 1999 the great concert hall, headquarters of the OBC, went into operation; in 2005 the School of Music of Catalonia (ESMUC) moved there, and in 2006 the Multi-Purpose Hall and the Chamber Hall opened. The Museu is the last piece in this ensemble which seeks to bring music nearer to all publics from a cultural and heritage-based standpoint.

The author of the museological project of the new Museu de la Música is Romà Escalas, the Museum's director, and the museographical part has been the responsibility

of architects from Dani Freixes' office, Lali González and Vicenç Bou, who have broad experience in exhibitions and inside architecture and who have worked in collaboration with Andreu Arriola in areas concerning the adaptation of the building. These people are committed to an innovative Museum concept in which the new audiovisual technologies have an important presence and the collections of musical documents and instruments are explained through acoustic, visual references as well as objects and texts. The aim is to offer broad sectors of the public a sensitive pedagogical experience of music through a panorama extending from its origins and constituent elements to the music of today. Since 2012 Jaume Ayats is the director.

Nowadays, more than 40,000 people are visiting yearly the permanent exhibition of the Museu (see WR 3), among which 17,000 students. Lately the museum has displayed large temporary exhibitions such as *Eolssigu! The sounds of Korea* (2017-2018), *Granados, de París a Goya* (2017-2018), *Guitar ON/OFF* (2016), *Voices of the Mediterranean* (2015), *Phonos, 40 years of electronic music in Barcelona* (2014-2015), *The musics of 1714s* (2014) and *Musical sCULpTUREs* (2013-2014) (see WR 4).

We have several publications, such an e-book about Hauslaib's claviorgan and another one about the square piano of Zumpe, a catalogue, a guide and a historic chronology about the Museum, manuscript by Isaac Albéniz and Enric Granados in collaboration with Biblioteca de Catalunya, catalogue of any of the temporary exhibitions as *Eolssigu! The Sounds of Korea* or *Musical Sculptures*, or the disc *The Guitar of Lions*, were we could record four guitars (anonymous Lion Guitar, anonymous Italian Guitar, guitar by Antonio de Torres, and by Josef Pagés) (see WR 5).

Open Collections, future is coming

The digitisation of the Museum collections in recent years has enabled us to generate several layers of knowledge about the same object: the file with the organological documentation on an instrument, the image or identification image, the book or article that develops and spreads knowledge about it and even the sound or video or other information that enables us to understand the kaleidoscope of each piece. They all gradually come together in the catalogue of instruments, a central point of information that can also be found in the library or multimedia archive, for example. At present, and following many enhancements to the web application, the search results of the Online Collections section (which we internally refer to as "open collections") allow us to link (manually rather than using search engines and common interfaces, which would be the short- or medium-term goal) images, books from the library (with a link to the catalogue) and the exhibitions or activities in which a musical instrument has been included, and now we are able to add sound or video, recorded either by us or by our collaborators.

However, there are many instruments from which it is impossible to obtain their sound, either due to their condition, in order to preserve them or for many other reasons. In those cases, a solution has been found on external platforms such as YouTube or Spotify which, in spite of not featuring exactly the same instrument as the one kept at the Museum, give us the option of adding a visual and/or sound reference that is as close to it as possible.

A more recent process is a deep change to instrument descriptions which, in addition to the most purely organological information, will include the instruments' history, social context and use.

Here a brief description of the tool used for each collection, which will gradually and eventually converge into a single tool (the museum online catalogue):

- Online instruments catalogue (WR 6) (catalogue of instruments and works of art, around 3000 items): Description guidelines suggested by the CIMCIM (International Committee for Museums and Collections of Instruments and Music), which is part of the ICOM (International Council of Museums); and, of course, an automated database, Museum+, which does provide remote access to all the information on the pieces.
- Historical archive (WR 7): In recent years this has undergone an intense cataloguing process in an AtoM database, in accordance with the General International Standard Archival Description (ISAD) guidelines, under the Barcelona Open Challenge project (WR 8). In addition, it has been digitised (following metadata description guidelines such as Dublin Core) and made public, making around 50% of the documents (photographs, manuscripts, music scores) available on the Museum's website.
- Library (WR 9): Around of 4,500 specialised volumes on organology have been catalogued, in accordance with international standards (MARC21, RDA, AACR2), on a database created with the open-source software KOHA, and the collection can be consulted both locally and as part of the catalogue of the CCUC (Collective Catalogue of Universities of Catalonia).
- Sound collection: This is part of the library catalogue and already includes all the pianola rolls and other perforated techniques, a small portion of the 78 rpm record collection and wax cylinders. In total, around 13,000 sound recordings.
- Multimedia archive: This is managed with the municipal ClipFiles repository and allows us to catalogue the entire digital collection – from images to sound and video recordings, around 30,000 items – according to the minimum Dublin Core standards. With the exception of the images of instruments and the digitised historical archive collection, both of which can be accessed from their corresponding catalogues, the multimedia collection is not yet available for consultation on the website.

In fact, this last section, the Multimedia Archive, is starting to take on its full role: some heritage instruments are in such good condition that we can still – albeit rarely – hear them. This means that, in some cases, we can still choose to digitise sound using sound or video recordings. For example, all the points of view of the Zell's harpsichord (see WR 10).

WR = Web Resources

1. <<http://ajuntament.barcelona.cat/museumusica/en>>
2. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Palau_Bar%C3%B3_de_Quadras>
3. <<http://ajuntament.barcelona.cat/museumusica/en/exposicions/museum-of-music-of-barcelona-permanent-exhibition>>
4. <<http://ajuntament.barcelona.cat/museumusica/en/exhibitions/type/past>>
5. <<http://ajuntament.barcelona.cat/museumusica/en/publicacions>>
6. <<https://cataleg.museumusica.bcn.cat/?lang=en>>
7. <<https://arxiu.museumusica.bcn.cat>>
8. <<http://ajuntament.barcelona.cat/museumusica/ca/blog/bcn-open-challenge-larxiu-historic-del-museu-a-labast-de-tothom>>
9. <<https://catalegbiblioteca.museumusica.bcn.cat/>>
10. <https://cataleg.museumusica.bcn.cat/detall/fons_instruments/H309896/?lang=en&resultsetnav=5cb5c917e0d71>

THE BARCELONA MUSEUM OF MUSIC

FIGURE 1. The collection of guitars (photo: S. Guastevi).

FIGURE 2. Temporary exhibition *Eolssigu! Els sons de Corea* (Sound of Corea; photo: S. Guastevi).

FIGURE 3. Serpent (1600-1700 ca.; photo: S. Guastevi).

FIGURE 4. *Gamelan* group Penempaan Guntur (resident in the Museum; photo: S. Guastevi).

FIGURE 5. Claviorgan by Lorenz Hauslaib (c. 1600) and harpsichord by Carl Conrad Fleischer (Hamburg, 1720; photo: S. Guastevi).

